

Agrostophyllanthrol and isoagrostophyllanthrol, two novel diastereomeric phenanthropyran derivatives from the orchid *Agrostophyllum khasiyanum*[†]

P. L. Majumder*, Nirmalendu Mukhoti and Saswati Chattopadhyay (née Lahiri)

Department of Chemistry, University College of Science, 92, Acharya Prafulla Chandra Road, Kolkata-700 009, India

E-mail : priyalalm@hotmail.com

Manuscript received 11 November 2008, accepted 17 November 2008

Abstract : Agrostophyllanthrol and isoagrostophyllanthrol, two novel diastereomeric phenanthropyran derivatives were isolated from the orchid *Agrostophyllum khasiyanum* which earlier afforded eleven stilbenoids, viz. the two dimeric phenanthrene derivatives agrostinin [2,2',7,7'-tetrahydroxy-4,4',6,6'-tetramethoxy-1,1'-biphenanthryl] and agrostinidin [2,2',6,6'-tetrahydroxy-4,4',7,7'-tetramethoxy-1,1'-biphenanthryl], eight phenanthropyran derivatives imbricatin [2,7-dihydroxy-6-methoxy-9,10-dihydro-5*H*-phenanthro[4,5-*bcd*]pyran], agrostophyllidin [7-hydroxy-2,6-dimethoxy-9,10-dihydro-5*H*-phenanthro[4,5-*bcd*]pyran], agrostophylloxidin [7-hydroxy-2,5,6-trimethoxy-5*H*-phenanthro[4,5-*bcd*]pyran], flaccidin [2,6-dihydroxy-7-methoxy-5*H*-phenanthro[4,5-*bcd*]pyran-5-one], isoflaccidin [2,7-dihydroxy-6-methoxy-5*H*-phenanthro[4,5-*bcd*]pyran-5-one], agrostophyllin [7-hydroxy-2,6-dimethoxy-5*H*-phenanthro[4,5-*bcd*]pyran], agrostophyllone [7-hydroxy-2,6-dimethoxy-5*H*-phenanthro[4,5-*bcd*]pyran-5-one], agrostophylloxin [2,6,7-trimethoxy-5*H*-phenanthro[4,5-*bcd*]pyran-5-one] and the bibenzyl derivative moscatilin [4,4'-dihydroxy-3,3',5-trimethoxybibenzyl]. The structures of agrostophyllanthrol and isoagrostophyllanthrol were established as 7-hydroxy-2,6-dimethoxy-5*H*-phenanthro[4,5-*bcd*]pyran-5(equat)ol and 7-hydroxy-2,6-dimethoxy-5*H*-phenanthro[4,5-*bcd*]pyran-5(ax)ol, respectively from various spectral and chemical evidence. Agrostophyllanthrol and isoagrostophyllanthrol, thus, represent two novel examples of otherwise conformational isomers becoming highly stable diastereomers due to unusual steric hindrance to conformational flipping.

Keywords : *Agrostophyllum khasiyanum*, Orchidaceae, agrostophyllanthrol and isoagrostophyllanthrol, phenanthropyran derivatives, otherwise conformational isomers becoming stable diastereomers, steric hindrance to conformational flipping.

Introduction

We reported earlier the isolation of a fairly large number of compounds from a series of Indian orchids. These phytochemicals encompass a wide variety of stilbenoids, viz. stilbene¹, bibenzyls², phenanthrenes and 9,10-dihydrophenanthrenes^{3,4} and their dimers⁵⁻⁹, phenanthropyrans and pyrones and their 9,10-dihydro derivatives¹⁰⁻¹⁵, fluorenones¹⁶ and a few other polyphenolics^{17,18}, several triterpenoids¹⁹⁻²¹, steroids of biogenetic importance²²⁻²⁴ and some simple aromatic compounds²⁵. As part of this general programme of research, we chemically investigated the orchid *Agrostophyllum khasiyanum* which earlier afforded eleven stilbenoids, viz. the phenanthropyran derivatives agrostophyllin¹⁵ (**1a**), agrostophylloxidin¹² (**1c**)

and the phenanthropyrone derivatives agrostophyllone¹² (**1d**), agrostophylloxin¹² (**1e**), flaccidin¹⁴ (**1f**) and isoflaccidin²⁶ (**1g**), the dihydrophenanthropyran derivatives imbricatin²⁷ (**2a**), agrostophyllidin¹² (**2b**), a bibenzyl derivative moscatilin²⁸ (**3**), and two dimeric phenanthrene derivatives agrostinin⁷ (**4a**) and agrostinidin⁷ (**4b**). Further chemical investigation of this orchid has now resulted in the isolation of yet two more phenanthropyran derivatives, designated agrostophyllanthrol and isoagrostophyllanthrol, the structures of which were established as 7-hydroxy-2,6-dimethoxy-5*H*-phenanthro[4,5-*bcd*]pyran-5(equat)ol (**1h**) and 7-hydroxy-2,6-dimethoxy-5*H*-phenanthro[4,5-*bcd*]pyran-5(ax)-ol[≠] (**1j**), respectively, from various spectral and chemical evidence.

[†]Dedicated to Professor Suresh C. Ameta on his 60th birthday.

*Although **1h**, **1j** and their derivatives were designated by systematic nomenclature, the phenanthrene numbering system is followed in this paper for convenience of ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectral comparison.

- 1a** : R¹=R⁴=Me, R²,R³=H, R⁵=H
1b : R¹=R⁴=Me, R²,R³=H, R⁵=Ac
1c : R¹=R⁴=Me, R²=OMe(ax), R³=R⁵=H
1d : R¹=R⁴=Me, R²,R³=O, R⁵=H
1e : R¹=R⁴=R⁵=Me, R²,R³=O
1f : R¹=R⁴=H, R²,R³=O, R⁵=Me
1g : R¹=R⁵=H, R²,R³=O, R⁴=Me
1h : R¹=R⁴=Me, R²=OH (equat.), R³=R⁵=H
1i : R¹=R⁴=Me, R²=OH (equat.), R³=H, R⁵=Ac
1j : R¹=R⁴=Me, R²=OH(ax.), R³=R⁵=H
1k : R¹=R⁴=Me, R²=OH(ax.), R³=H, R⁵=Ac

- 2a** : R¹=R²=H
2b : R¹=Me, R²=H
2c : R¹=Me, R²=Ac

3

- 4a** : R¹=H, R²=Me
4b : R¹=Me, R²=H

Results and discussion

Both agrostophyllanthrol and isoagrostophyllanthrol were shown to have the same molecular formula, C₁₇H₁₄O₅, from elemental analysis and their mass spectrometrically derived molecular weight 298. The UV

absorptions of the compounds [**1h** : λ_{max}^{EtOH} 219, 262, 286, 344 and 360 nm (log ε 2.70, 4.80, 3.40, 2.50 and 3.00); **1j** : λ_{max}^{EtOH} 219, 263, 304 and 317 nm (log ε 3.30, 4.10, 2.60 and 2.90) strikingly resemble those of phenanthropyran derivatives¹⁵. The phenolic nature of

the compounds was indicated by their characteristic colour reactions, alkali-induced bathochromic shifts of their UV maxima [**1h** : $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{EtOH}-0.1 (M) \text{NaOH}}$ 231, 285 and 308 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 3.00, 4.90 and 4.00); **1j** : $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{EtOH}-0.1 (M) \text{NaOH}}$ 230, 280 and 325 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 3.20, 3.90 and 3.00)] and by their IR absorptions at 3280 and 3300 cm^{-1} , respectively. The presence of one phenolic hydroxyl group in both **1h** and **1j** was confirmed by the formation of their respective monoacetyl derivatives with Ac_2O and pyridine. Thus, **1h** and **1j** formed the monoacetyl derivatives, $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_6$ ($[\text{M}]^+$ at m/z 340), m.p. 152 °C and $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_6$ ($[\text{M}]^+$ at m/z 340), m.p. 175 °C, respectively.

The 300 MHz ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) spectra of **1h** and **1j** showed signals for one phenolic hydroxyl proton [**1h** : δ 6.32 (1H, br.s); **1j** : δ 5.60 (1H, br.s)] and two aromatic methoxyl groups [**1h** : δ 3.03 and 3.95 (each 3H, s); **1j** : 3.95 and 4.01 (each 3H, s)]. The ^1H NMR spectra of **1h** and **1j** showed a two-proton ill-resolved AB-quartet at δ 7.61 and δ 7.59, respectively, which is typical of H-9 and H-10 of phenanthrene derivatives³. The absence of any downfield aromatic proton signal at *ca.* δ 9.0, characteristic of H-4 and H-5 of phenanthrene derivatives, in the spectrum of both the compounds suggests that both C-4 and C-5 of these compounds are substituted. The spectra of **1h** and **1j** exhibited a one-proton singlet at δ 6.63 and δ 6.60, respectively. Each of these signals may be attributed to a lactol methine proton present in these compounds. **1h** and **1j** may, therefore, be assumed to contain a lactol bridge flanked between C-4 and C-5. The spectrum of both the compounds also exhibited signals for three aromatic protons [**1h** : δ 6.90 and 7.10 (each 1H, d, J 1.8 Hz) and 7.39 (1H, s); **1j** : δ 7.10 and 7.30 (each 1H, d, J 1.8 Hz) and 7.38 (1H, s)]. Two of these three aromatic protons appeared as a pair of doublets corresponding to two *meta* coupled protons which were assigned to H-6 and H-8, respectively, placing the methoxyl group at C-7 as in **1a**. The remaining aromatic proton signal must then correspond to H-1 with substituents at C-2, C-3 and C4. The placement of the lone phenolic hydroxyl group at C-2 in both **1h** and **1j** was corroborated by the observed lowfield shifts of their H-1 resonance [**1i** : δ 7.56 (1H, s); **1k** : δ 7.57 (1H, s)] by *ca.* 0.17 ppm in the ^1H NMR spectra of their acetyl derivatives, **1i** and **1k**, respectively. The two aromatic methoxyl groups of **1h** and **1j** must, therefore, be located at C-3 and C-7 as in **1a**. It is interesting to note that the difference between the ^1H NMR spectra of **1h** and **1j** and their respective acetates **1i** and **1k** lies essentially in the chemical shifts of their aromatic methoxyl protons which ap-

peared in the normal region in the spectra of **1j** and **1k**, similar to those of **1a**. [**1j** : δ 3.95 and 4.01 (each 3H, s); **1k** : δ 3.86 and 3.89 (each 3H, s)], while the protons of one of the two methoxyl groups in the spectra of **1h** and **1i** showed remarkable upfield shifts [**1h** : δ 3.03 (3H, s); **1i** : δ 2.96 (3H, s)], the other methoxyl group appeared in the normal region [**1h** : δ 3.95 (3H, s); **1i** : δ 4.01 (3H, s)].

Further evidence in support of the structures of **1h** and **1j** was provided by the ^{13}C NMR spectral data of their more soluble monoacetyl derivatives **1i** and **1k**, respectively (Table 1). The degree of protonation of each carbon atom was determined by DEPT experiments and

Table 1. ^{13}C NMR spectral data of **1i**, **1k** and **1b**

C	Chemical shifts (δ ppm)*		
	1i	1k	1b
1	121.6	121.6	119.3
2	142.6	142.3	142.1
3	145.6	146.1	145.1
4	119.5	119.8	120.0
4a	122.9	122.4	122.4
4b	115.3	115.3	111.4
5	150.4	150.1	152.9
6	102.0	102.4	101.1
7	160.1	159.7	159.6
8	103.0	103.0	101.5
8a	132.1	132.3	131.6
9	126.1 ^a	126.0 ^a	125.6 ^a
10	125.9 ^a	125.8 ^a	125.4 ^a
10a	124.7	124.3	124.2
Ar-OCH(R)-Ar	89.47	89.5	63.7
	(R = OH)	(R = OH)	(R = H)
-OCH ₃	55.5	56.1	55.0
	61.4	61.5	61.0
ArOCOCH ₃	170.0	168.5	168.5
	20.7	20.6	20.3

*Spectra were run in CDCl_3 and the chemical shifts were measured with $\delta_{(\text{TMS})} = \delta_{(\text{CDCl}_3)} + 76.9$ ppm.

^aValues are interchangeable in each column.

the assignments of the carbon chemical shifts of **1i** and **1k** were made by comparison with the δ_{C} values of **1b**, a structurally related compound. The ^{13}C NMR spectra of **1i** and **1k** showed overall similarities with that of **1b**, except the chemical shifts of the methine carbons of the lactol bridge. Thus, the δ_{C} values of all but the lactol methine carbons, C-5 and C-6 of **1i** and **1k** were virtually

identical with those of the corresponding carbon atoms of **1b**, indicating identical substitution pattern in the aromatic rings of all the three compounds. In the spectra of **1i** and **1k**, the oxymethylene carbon of **1b** resonating at δ_C 63.7 were replaced by methine carbon signals at δ_C 89.47 and 89.5, respectively, which corresponded to their respective lactol methine carbons. The upfield shifts of C-5 of **1i** and **1k** by *ca.* 2.5 ppm and the downfield shifts of their C-6 by *ca.* 1.0 ppm compared with the corresponding carbon atoms of **1b** were also in agreement with the replacement of the oxymethylene bridge of **1b** by a lactol moiety in both **1i** and **1k** and hence in **1h** and **1j**.

The structures of **1h** and **1j** were finally confirmed by

the following chemical correlations (Scheme 1). Thus, reduction of both **1h** and **1j** with NaBH_4 in MeOH afforded **1a**, indicating the presence of a hydroxyl function at the oxymethylene carbon in both agrostophyllanthrol and isoagrostophyllanthrol. Again, **1c** was produced from both **1h** and **1j** by the action of MeOH in 1 (M) H_2SO_4 or by $\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{O}$ in MeOH. Thus, the above chemical correlations proved beyond doubt the presence of lactol function in both **1h** and **1j**. The only difference between **1h** and **1j** may be due to the difference in orientation of their lactol OH, attached to the chiral carbon atom.

Having established the gross structures of **1h** and **1j**, it now remains to ascertain the stereochemistry of the

Scheme 1. Chemical transformation reactions of agrostophyllanthrol (**1h**) and isoagrostophyllanthrol (**1j**).

compounds and their conformational aspects (Scheme 2). From a naive consideration of the structures of **1h** and **1j**, it appears that each of them should be optically active, since each of them has a chiral center at the lactol methine

1i' and **1i''** and **1k'** and **1k''**. A decision between the two alternative possibilities for each diastereomer was made by the chemical shifts of the protons of one of their aromatic methoxyl groups and those of the corresponding

Scheme 2. Conformational aspects of agrostophyllanthrol and isoagrostophyllanthrol.

carbons. Construction of Dreiding models for the gross structures of **1h** and **1j** show that they may exist as four stereoisomers **1h'**, **1h''**, **1j'** and **1j''** comprising a pair of diastereomers, each of which being a racemic mixture as evident from the fact that both **1h** and **1j** were found to be optically inactive. **1h** and **1j** may, therefore, be represented by the alternative *dl*-pairs of **1h'** and **1h''** and **1j'** and **1j''** and their respective acetates by the *dl*-pairs of

protons of their respective acetyl derivatives. In **1j'** and **1j''** and the corresponding acetates **1k'** and **1k''**, the aromatic methoxyl group at C-3 being far off from the lactol OH would be expected to have their protons resonating at the normal region similar to those of the other methoxyl group at C-7 of the above compounds. On the other hand, in **1h'** and **1h''** and hence in the corresponding acetates **1i'** and **1i''**, the aromatic methoxyl group at C-3 being

flanked by the much closer lactol OH and the hydroxyl group at C-2 (acetoxy group at C-2 in **1h'** and **1h''**) are thus forced out of plane of the aromatic ring. Consequently, the protons of the aromatic methoxyl group at C-3 in **1h'** and **1h''** as well as in **1i'** and **1i''** would be expected to resonate at an upfield position. Now, the appearance of the protons of both the aromatic methoxyl groups at C-3 and C-7 in the ^1H NMR spectra of **1j** and its acetate **1k** at the normal positions [**1j** : δ 3.95 and 4.01; **1k** : δ 3.89 and 3.94] suggests that they are the *dl*-pairs of **1j'** and **1j''** and **1k'** and **1k''**, respectively. On the other hand, the upfield resonances of the protons of one of the aromatic methoxyl groups of **1h** and its acetate **1i** [**1h** : δ 3.03 and 3.95; **1k** : δ 2.96 and 4.01] imply that they must be the *dl*-pairs of **1h'** and **1h''** and **1i'** and **1i''**, respectively. Looking at the conformational structures **1h'**, **1h''**, **1j'** and **1j''** of the four possible stereoisomers constructed from the Dreiding models of **1h** and **1j**, it is apparent that **1h'** and **1h''** are the flipped forms of **1j'** and **1j''**, respectively. The same relation exists between **1i'** and **1i''** and **1k'** and **1k''**. But while the conformers **1a'** and **1a''** of **1a** having no lactol OH are readily interconvertible at room temperature, no equilibrium between **1h** and **1j** was observed at room temperature. In fact, the two compounds are quite stable and were isolated as distinctly different compounds. That they are not interconverted under the experimental conditions of isolation prompted the present investigator to study the extent of their stability at higher temperatures. Accordingly, both **1i** and **1k** were separately heated in boiling EtOAc (78 °C) for 8 h. But no change was observed in each case. The solutions of **1i** and **1k** in EtOAc were then separately heated in Teflon-screw-capped glass tube at 130–135 °C in an oil bath for 1 h. But even under this condition no change was observed in each of these cases, indicating that flipping of **1i'** to **1k''** and **1i''** to **1k'** was not taking place even at this temperature. But when the above solutions of **1i** and **1k** in the aforesaid sealed tubes were separately heated at 140–145 °C for 1 h, the resultant solution in each case showed the presence of both the compounds [monitored by TLC] indicating that equilibration between **1i** and **1k** started slowly only at 140 °C. When the above solutions in the same tubes were separately heated to 140–145 °C for a further period of 5 h, the resultant solution in the tube originally containing pure **1i** showed the presence of **1i** and **1k** in the ratio of *ca.* 1 : 3, while the solution in the tube originally containing pure **1k** indicated the presence of **1k** and **1i** in the ratio of *ca.* 3 : 1. In the above and subsequent thermal studies the conversion of **1i** to **1k** and vice versa was

monitored by TLC [the acetyl derivatives of the two isomers have distinctly different R_f values in petrol-EtOAc (3 : 1) solvent system] and the ratio of **1i** and **1k** and other compounds in the mixture obtained after heating **1i** and **1k** at different temperatures for different time intervals was determined from the integrated intensities of the readily identifiable signals for the protons of their methoxyl group at C-3 in the ^1H NMR spectrum of the residue obtained in each case. When the above solutions were separately heated for a further period of 3 h, the composition of the two isomers remain unchanged in each case, indicating the attainment of equilibrium between **1i** and **1k**. This suggests that the flipping of **1i** and **1k** and vice versa, occurs only at such a high temperature. When the sealed tubes containing the above equilibrium mixtures of **1i** and **1k** were heated to 150–155 °C for a further period of 2 h, TLC of the resultant solutions showed the presence of a highly polar compound [which did not move from the base line even with EtOAc as the solvent system as indicated by the iodine stained spot in the chromatogram] and **1i** and **1k**. Heating the above solutions for a further period of 2 h at 165–170 °C the resultant solutions were found to contain mostly the polar compound and traces of **1h** and **1j** and their acetates. Each of these solutions [solutions **A** and **B**] was divided into two equal parts. One half of the solution **A** and one half of the solution **B** were separately warmed with a few drops of water and the resultant solution in each case, showed the total absence of the polar compound and were found to contain mostly **1j** (Scheme 3). The remaining one half of solutions **A** and **B** were separately evaporated and the residues were subjected to ^1H NMR spectral analysis. The ^1H NMR spectra of the two residues were virtually identical and showed signals at δ 9.83 (s), 7.59 (s), 7.45 (s), 7.39 and 7.26 (each, br.s), 6.21 (s), 4.01 (s) and 3.97 (s) for the major compound and those for traces of **1h**, **1j** and their acetates. The signal at δ 9.83 in the ^1H NMR spectrum of the major compound may be attributed to a proton of the oxonium moiety $\text{Ar-O}^+=\text{CH-Ar}$ of a dibenzopyrylium salt (Scheme 3), while those at δ 7.59, 7.45, 7.39, 7.26, 6.21, 4.01 and 3.97 corresponded to H-9, H-10, H-1, H-8, H-6, a phenolic hydroxyl proton and two aromatic methoxyl groups, respectively, of a phenanthrene derivative. Although the above polar compound could not be isolated, the above ^1H NMR spectral data of the compound suggest a dibenzopyrylium structure (**1p**) for the compound (Scheme 3).

The above compound when separately warmed with MeOH and EtOH, afforded **1c** (the congener stilbenoid) and the corresponding ethyl ether **1q**, respectively. The

Scheme 3. Thermal changes of **1i** and **1k** at elevated temperatures and their chemical changes.

structure of **1q** was established from its 1H NMR spectral data [1H NMR : δ 1.23 (3H, t; $-OCH_2CH_3$), 3.87 and 3.89 (each 3H, s; $2 \times ArOMe$), 4.07 (2H, q; $-O-CH_2CH_3$), 5.65 (br.s, disappeared on deuterium exchange; Ar-OH), 6.06 (1H, s; Ar-O-CH(OEt)Ar'), 6.75 (1H, d, J 1.8 Hz; H-6), 6.89 (1H, d, J 1.8 Hz; H-8), 7.47 (1H, s; H-1) and 7.61 (2H, s; H-9 and H-10)]. It seems likely that the polar compound **1p** is formed through the intermediacy of **1o** generated from **1k** by the elimination of the stereochemically favourable axial lactol OH having an adjacent donor oxygen atom. The $\overset{\ominus}{O}H$ thus eliminated, during the formation of **1o**, presumably hydrolyses the acetate functions of **1o**, **1i** and **1k**. This is evident from the fact that the polar compound **1p** is devoid of any acetate function and was found to contain a phenolic hydroxyl group. The $\overset{\ominus}{O}H$ thus eliminated in the process is

consumed in the hydrolysis of the acetate function of **1i**, **1k** and **1o**, and the oxonium species of **1p** thus survives from the attack by the eliminated $\overset{\ominus}{O}H$. The formation of **1j**, **1c** and **1q** from the polar compound **1p** may be assumed to involve in the nucleophilic attack from the less hindered axial side by H_2O , MeOH and EtOH, respectively, at the carbon atom of the oxonium species of **1p**. The possibility of the polar compound having a phenolic aldehydic structure (**1n**) seems unlikely in view of the fact that (i) a compound of the structure **1n** should not have such high polarity, (ii) it is difficult to rationalize the formation of **1c** and **1q** by the reaction of **1n** with MeOH and EtOH, respectively, under the reaction conditions stated above (Scheme 3). The formation of **1o** and **1p** thus facilitates the shift of the equilibrium from **1i** to **1k**. Such high energy required for the conversion of **1i** to

1k and vice versa may be rationalized by the fact that at the transition state of flipping of **1i** to **1k** and **1k** to **1i** the lactol OH and the OMe group at C-3 so heavily impinge on each other appearing well within their van der Waals radii that flipping of **1i** and **1k** and vice versa involves an unusually high activation energy.

However, conversion of **1h** to **1j** was readily achieved chemically by opening of the lactol ring by the action of 1 (M) NaOH solution. Thus, when **1h** and **1j** were separately treated with 1 (M) NaOH solution, and the resultant solutions were acidified, **1h** was completely converted

to **1j**, but the latter remained unchanged. The above observation may be rationalized by the assumption that on treatment with alkali both **1h** and **1j** form the same intermediate aldehydic phenoxide ion **1r** by opening of the lactol ring. Recyclisation of **1r** generated from both **1h** and **1j** afforded the thermodynamically more stable isomer **1j** in each case (Scheme 4). In this reaction thus only **1h** is converted to **1j**, the latter apparently remaining unchanged. Again, treatment of **1h** and **1j**, separately with $\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{O}/\text{MeOH}$ or 1 (M) aq. $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4/\text{MeOH}$ gave only the thermodynamically more stable axial lactol methyl ether derivative **1c** (Scheme 4).

Scheme 4. Chemical transformations of agrostophyllanthrol (**1h**) and isoagrostophyllanthrol (**1j**).

The formation of **1c** from **1h** and **1j** in the above reactions may be assumed to involve the intermediacy of dibenzopyrylium salt [**1p**] generated by the removal of the lactol OH followed by nucleophilic attack by MeOH from the less hindered axial side. Thus, from its mode of formation **1c** may be represented as the *dl*-pair of **1c'** and **1c''** in which the lactol methyl ether group is axially oriented (Scheme 4).

Agrostophyllanthrol (**1h**) and isoagrostophyllanthrol (**1j**) thus represent two novel examples of otherwise conformational isomers becoming highly stable diastereomers due to unusual steric hindrance to conformational flipping.

Experimental

M.p.s. : uncorr. CC : silica gel (100–200 mesh). TLC : silica gel G. IR : KBr discs. ¹H and ¹³C NMR : 300 MHz and 75 MHz, respectively. NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ using TMS as int. standard. Chemical shifts were expressed in δ (ppm). MS : direct inlet system, 70 eV. All analyt. samples were routinely dried over P₂O₅ for 24 h *in vacuo* and were tested for purity by TLC and MS. The petrol used had b.p. 60–80 °C. Anhydrous Na₂SO₄ was used for drying organic solvents.

Plant materials :

Agrostophyllum khasianum Lindl. was collected from Kalimpong (Darjeeling, India) in October 1995. A voucher specimen (Majumder s.n.) was deposited in the Herbarium of the Department of Botany, University of Calcutta (CUH).

Isolation of agrostophyllanthrol (1h), isoagrostophyllanthrol (1j), 1a, 1c, 1d, 1e, 1f, 1g, 2a, 2b, 3, 4a and 4b :

Air-dried finely powdered whole plant of *A. khasianum* (5 kg) was kept soaked in MeOH (10 L) for 4 weeks. The MeOH extract was concentrated to *ca.* 100 ml, diluted with H₂O (750 ml) and exhaustively extracted with Et₂O. The Et₂O extract was fractionated into acidic and nonacidic fractions with 2 M NaOH. The aq. alkaline solution was acidified in the cold with conc. HCl and the liberated solids were extracted with Et₂O, washed with H₂O, dried and the solvent removed. The Et₂O extract containing the non-acidic constituents (left after treatment with 2 M NaOH) was also washed with H₂O, dried and the solvent removed. The residues containing the acidic and non-acidic (neutral) compounds were separately chromatographed.

Chromatography of the acidic fraction :

The petrol-EtOAc (20 : 1) eluate gave a semisolid

mass containing agrostophyllin (**1a**), agrostophyllone (**1d**), agrostophylloxidin (**1c**) and agrostophyllidin (**2b**). The above mixture was then subjected to MPLC using petrol-EtOAc (2 : 1) as the solvent. The early fractions in the above MPLC gave a mixture of **1a** and **2b** and the later fractions afforded a solid containing **1d** and **1c**. The mixture of **1a** and **2b** and that of **1d** and **1c** could not be separated even on repeated column chromatography. Both the residues were separately acetylated with Ac₂O and pyridine in the usual manner and the two acetylated mixtures were separately subjected to column chromatography. The early fractions of petrol-EtOAc (50 : 1) in the column chromatography of the acetylated mixture of **1a** and **2b** afforded pure agrostophyllidin acetate **2c** (0.015 g) as a semisolid mass and the later fractions of the same eluate gave pure acetyl derivative of **1a** [**1b**] (0.1 g), crystallized from petrol-EtOAc mixture, m.p. 125 °C.

A solution of **2c** (0.01 g) in 5 ml 2 M methanolic HCl was refluxed for 2 h. The MeOH was removed under reduce pressure and the residue was extracted with Et₂O, washed with H₂O, dried and the solvent removed. The residue was chromatographed. The petrol-EtOAc (30 : 1) eluate gave pure **2b** (0.008 g) as an amorphous powder. Similar acid-hydrolysis of **1b** afforded **1a**, m.p. 86 °C.

The acetylated mixture of (**1d**) and (**1c**) on repeated chromatography gave in the early fractions of petrol-EtOAc (50 : 1) eluate pure acetyl derivative of **1c** (0.03 g), crystallized from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 196 °C and pure acetyl derivative of **1d** (0.04 g) in the later fractions of the same eluate. It was also crystallized from the same solvent mixture, m.p. 220 °C. Mild alkaline hydrolysis of the acetyl derivatives of **1c** and **1d** with 0.5 (M) ethanolic NaOH, followed by usual work-up and chromatography afforded **1c** and **1d** as amorphous powder and semisolid mass, respectively.

The early fractions of the petrol-EtOAc (10 : 1) eluate from the main chromatographic column gave a semisolid mass containing agrostophyllanthrol (**1h**) and isoagrostophyllanthrol (**1j**). The above mixture on repeated MPLC using petrol-EtOAc (2 : 1) as the solvent finally afforded pure **1h** (0.25 g) and **1j** (0.2 g), both as pale yellow semisolid mass. Agrostophyllanthrol (**1h**) (Found : C, 68.44; H, 4.67. C₁₇H₁₄O₅ requires : C, 68.46; H, 4.69%); UV λ_{max} nm : 219, 262, 286, 344 and 360 (log ε 2.70, 4.80, 3.40, 2.50 and 3.00); IR ν_{max} cm⁻¹ : 3280 (OH), 1610, 1590, 1440, 1060, 855 and 720 (aromatic nucleus); ¹H NMR : δ 3.03 and 3.95 (each 3H, s; 2 × Ar-OMe), 6.32 (1H, br.s.; Ar-OH), 6.63 (1H, s; Ar-O-CH(OH)Ar'),

6.90 (1H, d, J 1.8 Hz; H-6), 7.1 (1H, d, J 1.8 Hz; H-8), 7.37 (1H, s; H-1) and 7.46 (2H, ill-resolved AB quartet; H-9 and H-10). Isoagrostophyllanthrol (**1j**) (Found : C, 68.43; H, 4.66. $C_{17}H_{14}O_5$ requires : C, 68.46; H, 4.69%); UV λ_{\max} nm : 219, 263, 304 and 317 (log ϵ 3.30, 4.10, 2.60 and 2.90); IR ν_{\max} cm^{-1} : 3300 (OH), 1625, 1520, 1495, 1020, 980 and 815 (aromatic nucleus); 1H NMR : δ 3.95 and 4.01 (each 3H, s; Ar-OMe), 5.60 (1H, br.s.; Ar-OH), 6.60 (1H, s; Ar-O-CH(OH)Ar'), 7.10 (1H, d, J 1.8 Hz; H-6), 7.30 (1H, d, J 1.8 Hz; H-8), 7.38 (1H, s; H-1) and 7.51 (2H, ill-resolved AB quartet; H-9 and H-10). **1h** and **1j** were separately acetylated with Ac_2O and pyridine in the usual manner to give the corresponding acetyl derivatives **1i** and **1k**, respectively, both as amorphous powder. **1i** (Found : C, 67.01; H, 4.68. $C_{19}H_{16}O_6$ requires : C, 67.06; H, 4.70%); IR ν_{\max} cm^{-1} : 3460 (OH), 1770 and 1230 (OAc), 1650, 1470, 1319, 1170, 1020, 940, 860 and 760 (aromatic nucleus); 1H NMR : δ 2.28 (3H, s; Ar-OAc), 2.96 and 4.01 (each 3H, s; $2 \times$ Ar-OMe), 6.81 (1H, s; Ar-O-CH(OH)Ar'), 6.99 (1H, d, J 1.8 Hz; H-6), 7.19 (1H, d, J 1.8 Hz; H-8), 7.56 (1H, s; H-1) and 7.61 (2H, ill-resolved AB quartet; H-9 and H-10); MS m/z (rel. int.) : 340 (M^+ , 6), 324 (12), 323 (80), 298 (20), 282 (18), 281 (60), 267 (10), 266 (62), 252 (5), 251 (9), 239 (3), 238 (5), 237 (10), 224 (2), 223 (10), 222 (5), 209 (2), 195 (5), 194 (3) and 166 (5). **1k** : IR ν_{\max} cm^{-1} : 3400 (OH), 1745 and 1220 (OAc), 1610, 1575, 1500, 1465, 1375, 1275, 1130, 1030, 925 and 865 (aromatic nucleus); 1H NMR : δ 2.34 (3H, s; Ar-OAc), 3.89 and 3.94 (each 3H, s; $2 \times$ Ar-OMe), 6.85 (1H, s; Ar-O-CH(OH)Ar'), 7.18 (1H, d, J 2.1 Hz; H-6), 7.40 (1H, d, J 2.1 Hz; H-8), 7.57 (1H, s; H-1) and 7.59 (2H, ill-resolved AB quartet; H-9 and H-10); MS m/z (rel. int.) : 340 (M^+ , 20), 324 (12), 323 (60), 298 (20), 282 (16), 281 (80), 267 (10), 266 (60), 252 (94), 251 (10), 239 (3), 238 (5), 237 (12), 224 (2), 223 (10), 222 (5), 209 (2), 195 (5), 194 (3) and 166 (5).

The later fractions of petrol-EtOAc (10 : 1) eluate from the main column afforded imbricatin **2a** (0.05 g), crystallized from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 145 °C.

Washing the main column with petrol-EtOAc (7 : 1) gave moscatilin **3** (0.08 g), crystallized from the same solvent mixture, m.p. 84 °C. Further elution of the above column with petrol-EtOAc (5 : 1) afforded, in the early fractions, flaccidin **1f** (0.05 g), crystallized from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 325 °C (d). The later fractions of the same eluate gave isoflaccidin **1g** (0.04 g), crystallized from the same solvent mixture, m.p. 300 °C (d).

The petrol-EtOAc (2 : 1) eluate from the main column

afforded a mixture of agrostinin (**4a**) and agrostinidin (**4b**). The mixture on repeated MPLC finally afforded pure agrostinin **4a** (0.05 g) and agrostinidin **4b** (0.03 g), both as amorphous powder.

Chromatography of the non-acidic fraction :

The nonacidic part of the methanolic extract of *A. khasiyanum* was similarly chromatographed. The petrol-EtOAc (30 : 1) eluate gave agrostophylloxin (**1e**) (0.06 g), crystallized from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 226 °C.

Reduction of agrostophyllanthrol (**1h**) and isoagrostophyllanthrol (**1j**) with $NaBH_4$:

To a solution of 0.03 g of each of **1h** and **1j** in 15 ml of MeOH were added separately 0.01 g of $NaBH_4$ with stirring. The mixtures were heated under reflux on boiling water-bath for 1 h. MeOH was removed under reduced pressure and residues were acidified with 2 M HCl in the cold and extracted separately with Et_2O , washed with water, dried and the solvent removed to give **1a**, crystallized from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 86 °C, in both the cases, identified by direct comparison (m.m.p. and superimposeable IR spectra).

Thermal interconversion of agrostophyllanthrol acetate (**1i**) and isoagrostophyllanthrol acetate (**1k**), formation of the polar compound **1p** and the reaction of **1p** with H_2O , MeOH and EtOH :

Four sets of solutions of **1i** [each containing 0.03 g of **1i**] in EtOAc (each 5 ml) were separately heated in Teflon-screw-capped sealed tubes, one at 140–145 °C for 1 h, the second at the same temperature for a further period of 8 h, the third at 150–155 °C for 2 h (after heating for 6 h at 140–145 °C) and the fourth at 165–170 °C for 2 h (after heating first at 140–145 °C for 8 h and then 150–155 °C for 2 h) and the residues **A**, **B**, **C** and **D** obtained after evaporation of solvents in the four sets of experiments, respectively, were examined by TLC and 1H NMR. TLC of the residue **A** indicated the presence of **1i** and **1k** in ca. 9 : 1 ratio. The 1H NMR spectra of the residue **B** showed the presence of **1i** and **1k** in the ratio of 1 : 3 and that of **C** showed the presence of **1p**, **1k** and **1i**. The ratios of the compounds in the above residues were obtained from the integrated intensities of the signals of the protons of their methoxyl groups at C-3. The 1H NMR spectrum of the residue **D** (in $CDCl_3$) showed (besides the signals of traces of **1h**, **1i**, **1j** and **1k**) signals for **1p** : δ 3.97 and 4.01 (each 3H, s; $2 \times$ Ar-OMe), 6.21 (1H, br.s; Ar-OH), 7.26 and 7.39 (each, 1H, ill-resolved m -coupled doublet; H-6, H-8), 7.45 (1H, s; H-1), 7.59 (2H, s; H-9 and H-10) and 9.83 (1H, s, $Ar-O^+ = CH-Ar'$).

Four sets of solutions of **1k** [each containing 0.03 g of **1k**] in EtOAc (each 5 ml) were separately heated in a similar manner in Teflon-screw-capped sealed tubes, one at 140–145 °C for 1 h, the second at the same temperature for a further period of 8 h, the third at 150–155 °C for 2 h (after heating for 6 h at 140–145 °C) and the fourth at 165–170 °C for 2 h (after heating first at 140–145 °C for 8 h and then at 150–155 °C for 2 h) and the residues **A'**, **B'**, **C'** and **D'** obtained after evaporation of solvents in the four sets of experiments, respectively, were similarly examined by TLC and ¹H NMR. The ratios of **1k** and **1i** in **A'** and **B'** were found to be in the ratio of 1 : 9 and 3 : 1, respectively. The residue **C'** indicated the presence of **1p**, **1k** and **1i** similar to that of **C**. The ¹H NMR spectrum of the residue **D'** was virtually identical with that of the residue **D** obtained from **1k** and was found to contain predominantly the polar compound **1p** along with traces of **1h**, **1i**, **1j** and **1k**.

Residues **D** and **D'** were mixed up and divided into three equal parts. First part of the combined residue was treated with water (7 drops) and the resulting mixture was warmed and shaken for 5 min, extracted with EtOAc, dried and the solvent removed. The ¹H NMR spectra of the products showed the presence of isoagrostophyllanthrol (**1j**) as the major compound. The remaining two parts were separately treated with dry MeOH and EtOH (each 1 ml) and warmed on water bath with shaking for 5 min. Excess of MeOH and EtOH were removed and the residues were separately extracted with EtOAc, dried and the solvent removed. The residues were separately chromatographed. The petrol-EtOAc (2 : 1) eluate in the chromatography of the products obtained with MeOH gave agrostophylloxidin (**1c**) (0.018 g) as white amorphous solid. Chromatography of the products obtained with EtOH gave, in petrol-EtOAc (2 : 1) eluate **1q** (0.015 g). ¹H NMR: δ 1.23 (3H, t; -O-CH₂-CH₃), 3.87 and 3.89 (each 3H, s; 2 × ArOMe), 4.07 (2H, q; -O-CH₂-CH₃), 5.65 (br.s., disappeared on deuterium exchange; Ar-OH), 6.60 (1H, s; Ar-O-CH(OEt)Ar'), 6.75 (1H, d, *J* 1.8 Hz; H-6), 6.89 (1H, d, *J* 1.8 Hz; H-8), 7.47 (1H, s; H-1) and 7.61 (2H, s; H-9 and H-10).

Acknowledgement

The work was supported by the University Grants Commission (UGC) and the DST, New Delhi, India.

References

1. P. L. Majumder, M. Roychowdhury and S. Chakraborty, *Phytochemistry*, 1998, **49**, 2375.
2. P. L. Majumder, S. Guha and S. Sen, *Phytochemistry*, 1999, **52**, 1365.
3. P. L. Majumder, S. Sen and S. Majumder, *Phytochemistry*, 2001, **58**, 581.
4. P. L. Majumder, S. Laha and N. Dutta, *Phytochemistry*, 1982, **21**, 478.
5. P. L. Majumder, S. Pal and S. Majumder, *Phytochemistry*, 1999, **50**, 891.
6. P. L. Majumder, A. Pal and M. Joarder, *Phytochemistry*, 1990, **29**, 271.
7. P. L. Majumder, S. Banerjee, S. Lahiri, N. Mukhoti and S. Sen, *Phytochemistry*, 1998, **47**, 855.
8. P. L. Majumder and S. Banerjee, *Tetrahedron*, 1998, **44**, 7303.
9. P. L. Majumder, B. Rahaman, M. Roychowdhury and K. P. Dhara, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2008, **85**, 192.
10. P. L. Majumder, D. Bandyopadhyay and S. Joardar, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1982, 1131.
11. P. L. Majumder, S. Sen and S. Banerjee, *Tetrahedron*, 1999, **55**, 6691.
12. P. L. Majumder, S. Lahiri and N. Mukhoti, *Phytochemistry*, 1996, **42**, 1157.
13. P. L. Majumder and D. C. Maiti, *Phytochemistry*, 1988, **27**, 899.
14. P. L. Majumder and D. C. Maiti, *Phytochemistry*, 1989, **28**, 887.
15. P. L. Majumder and E. Sabzabadi, *Phytochemistry*, 1988, **27**, 1899.
16. P. L. Majumder and J. Chakraborty, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1989, **66**, 834.
17. P. L. Majumder, S. Lahiri and S. Pal, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1994, **71**, 645.
18. P. L. Majumder, S. Lahiri and N. Mukhoti, *Phytochemistry*, 1995, **40**, 271.
19. P. L. Majumder and S. Ghosal, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1991, **68**, 88.
20. P. L. Majumder, S. Majumder and S. Sen, *Phytochemistry*, 2003, **62**, 591.
21. P. L. Majumder and B. Rahaman, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **83**, 58.
22. P. L. Majumder and J. Chakraborty, *Tetrahedron*, 1985, **41**, 4973.
23. P. L. Majumder and A. Kar, *Phytochemistry*, 1989, **28**, 1487.
24. P. L. Majumder and S. Pal, *Phytochemistry*, 1990, **29**, 2717.
25. P. L. Majumder and S. Lahiri, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1989, **28**, 771.
26. P. L. Majumder and D. C. Maiti, *Phytochemistry*, 1991, **30**, 971.
27. P. L. Majumder and A. Sarkar, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1982, **21**, 829.
28. P. L. Majumder and R. C. Sen, *Phytochemistry*, 1987, **26**, 2121.

